

Velocities obtained as in (I), (II), (III) & (IV) were found to agree quite well and the mean of all these velocities was taken as the true particle velocity.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A potential of 200 volts from a set of storage batteries was applied to the cataphoretic cell. The drop in potential in the rectangular part of the cell, which was 5.75 cm. long, was calculated from a determination of the relative resistances of the liquid in the rectangular flat part of the cell and in the attached limbs.

The method of preparing the gels and saturating them with various cations have been described in Part I of this series of papers (*loc. cit.*).

The particles of the saturated gels, which were washed until the concentration of Cl⁻ ion in the filtrate was less than 1×10^{-5} (*loc. cit.*) were suspended in water, shaken, and allowed to settle to remove coarser particles by sedimentation. Time required for settling was calculated from Stokes' formula so that particles above diameter of 0.01 mm. could be removed by sedimentation, assuming them to be spherical. The cell was dismantled after each determination and cleansed thoroughly so that no appreciable error could be introduced by particles sticking to the walls of the cell.

The p_{11} values of the suspensions were determined by means of hydrogen and quinhydrone electrodes. The proportion of gel to water was 1 : 2.5 in all cases. Results are given in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Sample.	Saturating cation.	Cataphoretic velocity. μ /sec. volt/cm.	Temp.	p_{11} .
SiO ₂	...	-0.58	29.0	4.91
	Na	-1.11	29.5	5.20
	K	-0.78	29.0	5.59
	Ca	-0.56	30.0	5.22
	Mg	-0.76	29.0	5.54
Al ₂ O ₃	...	+0.83	29.5	5.87
	Na	+0.30	30.0	6.86
	K	+0.44	30.0	6.79
	Ca	+0.80	29.5	6.91
	Mg	+0.59	29.5	6.79
Fe ₂ O ₃	...	+0.48	29.5	5.88
	Na	+0.27	29.0	6.51
	K	+0.34	29.0	6.22
	Ca	+0.46	29.5	6.34
	Mg	+0.39	29.0	6.21

TABLE II.

Sample.	Saturating cation.	Cataphoretic velocity. $\mu/\text{sec. volt./cm.}$	Temp.	pH .
	...			5.04
$\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (Mixture I).	Na			6.42
$\frac{\text{SiO}_2}{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} = 4.37$	K			6.31
	Ca			6.23
	Mg			6.11
$\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (Mixture II)	...	-0.52	30.5	5.13
$\frac{\text{SiO}_2}{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} = 1.33$	Na	-0.99	30.0	6.41
	K	-0.93	30.0	6.39
	Ca	-0.58	30.0	6.66
	Mg	-0.77	29.5	6.42
$\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (Mixture III)	...			5.37
$\frac{\text{SiO}_2}{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} = 3.68$	Na			6.06
	K			5.91
	Ca			6.22
	Mg			6.10
$\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (Mixture IV)	...	-0.44	29.0	5.78
$\frac{\text{SiO}_2}{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} = 1.04$	Na	-0.85	29.0	6.10
	K	-0.68	30.0	5.87
	Ca	-0.49	29.5	6.37
	Mg	-0.64	29.0	6.31

TABLE III.

Saturating cation.	Anderson clay.	Mattson clay.	Author		
			SiO_2 .	$\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$.	$\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$.
Ca	100	100	100	100	100
Mg	99	...	135	132	130
K	134	...	140	160	140
Na	149	191	198	170	173
H	23	168	104	89	90

DISCUSSION.

The amount of free electrolyte occurring normally in laterite soil of this country of heavy rainfall is very small. In the present investigation, the gels, which are probable constituents of soil, may be assumed to correspond approximately to natural condition. The cataphoretic velocity was determined in suspensions of the samples in distilled water. During recent years this problem has been attacked from all sides. That the particle velocity is independent of size and shape has been shown by various investigators. A list of number of investigators together with the names of the materials with which the investigation was made has been given by Abramson (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 289). Mention may be made of the work of Abramson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 390) and Freundlich and Abramson (*loc. cit.*; *ibid.*, 1928, **133**, 51) who have shown that the velocity of particles of quartz, glass and clay is independent of size and shape between 3μ to 15μ . Recent investigation of Kemp (*loc. cit.*) on the cataphoretic mobility of silica and gamboge has shown that the mobility decreases with decreasing particle size. He accounts for this variation of mobility with particle size by Henry's equation (*Proc. Roy Soc.*, 1931, **A133**, 106)

$$v = \frac{X\sigma}{\eta K} \cdot \frac{Kb}{1 + Kb} f(Kb)$$

over a range of Kb , 2-330, where b is the radius and K is defined by the equation

$$K = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi e^2}{DkT} \sum n_i \gamma_i^2} = 3.28 \cdot 10^7 u \text{ at } 20^\circ.$$

According to Henry, however, no variation in the mobility could be expected with large particles in relatively strong solutions. Recently Mukherjee and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 372, 428) in an investigation on the cataphoretic velocity of colloidal particles, have made a critical study of the dependence of velocity on size, shape and ionic strength. They have shown that the velocity increases with the aggregation of colloidal particles in presence of an electrolyte and this behaviour has been explained from a consideration of Mukherjee's theory of ion adsorption. As stated previously, the presence of free electrolytes in the gels used in

this investigation was very small and the velocities were measured in distilled water. The particle size was 0.01 mm. and below. All the experiments were also conducted under identical conditions. Hence no appreciable error may be expected to be introduced in getting comparable results.

Kemp (*loc. cit.*) has shown that the mobilities of the particles of gamboge and silica show very little change with the p_n of the solution. The change in velocity with p_n of materials such as ferric oxide in the soil state has been studied by Hanzel and Ayres (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 36, 2930) and others. It will be seen from the tables that the p_n values of the gels used in the experiments all lie between 5 and 7. So the effect of difference of p_n on the velocity, if any, might be neglected and hence a study on the change of velocity with p_n of the particles was not made a part of the investigation.

In Tables I and II are given the p_n and cataphoretic velocity of the unmixed and mixed gels when saturated with different cations. In the case of the SiO_2 gel, Na increased the negative charge to a considerable extent, the cataphoretic speed being in the order $\text{Na} > \text{K} > \text{Mg} > \text{Ca} >$ electro-dialysed gel (which is an unsaturated hydrogen gel). The values of K- and Mg-saturated samples are very near to each other, where as the Ca-saturated sample gives a value which approaches that of the electro-dialysed materials. It will be observed from Table II that the mixed gels of $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, as obtained by mutual precipitation, also behave in the same way as the SiO_2 gel, the speed being in the order $\text{Na} > \text{K} > \text{Mg} > \text{Ca} >$ unsaturated H-gel. This order holds for the degree of dispersion of various soil colloidal materials shown by Gedroiz, (*Z. Ophytn. Agron.*, 1924, 22, 29).

In Table III are given the relative values of the mobility of clay particles as obtained by Mattson, Anderson and the author. From a comparison of the results it may be said that the data are in partial agreement with the observations of the investigators named above. Where as Anderson got the lowest value for H-clay, and Mattson obtained a value greater than that of Ca-clay, the values obtained in the present investigation for the unsaturated H-gel are nearer to the value of Ca-gel; but the values are slightly less in the case of the mixed gels and greater in case of SiO_2 . According to Keen ("The Physical Properties of the Soil," p. 190) however, the value of Anderson for H-clay is probably incorrect.

The gels of Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 , saturated with different cations are electropositive between the p_n range indicated (Table II). The order of effect of ions is again reversed in this case, being electro-dialysed gel $> \text{Ca} > \text{Mg} > \text{K} > \text{Na}$. Thus the effect of ions is quite marked in the value of mobility of the gel particles.

p_n values of the gels, saturated with different cations, are given in Tables I and II. The p_n values of pure SiO_2 , both gel and powder and of the supernatant liquid, have been given in Part I. An observation of the values of SiO_2 gel might suggest that the gel after saturation with the chlorides and continued washing till free from chlorine, may adsorb H^+ -ions from water on partial displacement of the metal ion with which the gel has been saturated.

It will be noticed that in all cases except in the case of SiO_2 gel, Na-saturated gel gives higher values than the K-saturated gel; and Ca-saturated gel gives higher value than the Mg-saturated gel. As expected, monovalent cations influence the p_n in the order of their hydration. But in case of bivalent cations this order of hydration does not hold. This may be ascribed to the special characteristics of Ca-saturated colloid observed by Gallay (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1925, 21, 464) who pointed out that Ca-soils, both artificial and natural, differ from all soils through their greater sensitivity to electrolytes. This view has also been confirmed by Aarnio (*First Int. Cong. Soil Sci.*, 1928, 2, 65) who observed that the reaction of calcium clay in water solution was always higher than that of Mg-clay.

It has been noted by various investigators that if a soil is adsorptively saturated with the ions of Ca, Mg, Na, and K and if there is no free hydrolysed salt in a soil, then the soil is either neutral or basic. But percolation brings exchange of the cations with hydrogen ions of water and makes the soil at the same time more acid. It will be seen from the tables that the p_n values of the gels never exceeded 7 and in case of SiO_2 -gel it became as low as 5.2. This low p_n is evidently due to the continued leaching during washing of the gels after saturation when probably there was a partial exchange of the metal ions with hydrogen ion.

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